

IMPLEMENTING VERTICAL INTEGRATION HEALTHCARE SERVICES IN A VIETNAMESE PRIVATE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM: A PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH

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VERTICALLY INTEGRATED HEALTHCARE DELIVERY SYSTEMS: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH

Vertical integration in healthcare involves the consolidation of various healthcare entities operating at different levels of the care continuum, functioning as a unified system. This strategic approach aims to improve patient care by enhancing comprehensiveness, continuity, and efficiency, patients outcomes ultimately leading to increased organizational effectiveness and profitability.

Definition: A vertically integrated healthcare system provides a broad range of services, either directly or through partnerships, encompassing a spectrum of care levels, such as primary care, specialty care, acute inpatient care, rehabilitation, long-term care, and home healthcare (Conrad et al 1990; Ramsay et al 2009).

Dimensions of Vertical Integration: Breadth of Integration: The range of diagnoses and services offered by the vertically integrated system. This could involve a comprehensive spectrum of Diagnosis Related Groups (DRGs). *Internal vs. External Sourcing:* The degree to which the system relies on internally developed services and resources compared to outsourcing to external providers.

Value Chain Integration: The number of stages in the value chain that are integrated or explicitly coordinated by and within the organization. A fully integrated system might encompass wellness programs, primary care, specialty care, acute inpatient care, long-term care, and home healthcare, effectively covering the entire care continuum. *Form of Integration:* The nature of coordination or ownership arrangements linking services within the system. *Health Insurance Integration:* A

unique "fifth dimension" in healthcare, where health insurance is integrated with health service delivery, creating a managed care model.

Figure 1: Illustration of vertical integration in hospital setting (mesolevel of integration)

Benefits and Challenges of Vertical Integration healthcare services

Evidence for Benefits: Primary Care as a Driver: Studies have shown that integrating primary care with secondary care services, particularly in areas where primary care practices are at risk of closure, can help manage demand pressure on acute hospital services, especially emergency care (Sidhu et al., 2022).

Improved Access and Coordination: Vertical integration can improve access to healthcare services, particularly in underserved communities, and can facilitate smoother transitions between different care levels, enhancing coordination and reducing fragmentation (Gröne et al., 2001).

Enhanced Efficiency and Quality: Some studies have shown improvements in efficiency, measured by reduced utilization and costs, as well as improvements in the quality of public health and medical services (Ramsay et al., 2009). Additionally, vertical integration has been linked to improved health provider-centered outcomes (knowledge and skills) and patient-centered outcomes (clinical outcomes, behavior, and satisfaction) (Wang et al., 2024).

Disadvantages and Evidences: Reduced Competition:Vertically integrated systems may reduce competition in the healthcare market, leading to higher prices

and reduced incentives for innovation. Research has shown that in regions with fewer competing healthcare organizations, costs tend to rise. For example, a study published in the *Journal of Health Economics* indicated that hospitals that are part of larger systems often charge higher prices due to a lack of competitive pressure. (Esther Gal-Or et al, 1999).

Limited Provider Choice: Patients may find themselves limited to a narrower range of healthcare providers and specialists within a vertically integrated system. This can lead to dissatisfaction among patients who prefer the freedom to choose their healthcare professionals. Surveys, such as those conducted by the Commonwealth Fund, have indicated that patients often value the ability to choose their doctors and may feel constrained in integrated models. *Potential for Conflict of Interest:* There may be conflicts of interest in vertically integrated systems, where certain services are prioritized over others due to financial incentives. For instance, a study published in the *New England Journal of Medicine* has highlighted concerns around integrated systems encouraging unnecessary referrals to their services rather than considering the most appropriate care for patients (Bodenheimer, T. (2008). *Administrative Complexity: Managing a wide range of services under one organization can lead to increased administrative complexity and inefficiency. Findings from the Health Affairs Health Policy Brief (2020) indicate that larger systems often face greater bureaucratic challenges which can slow down decision-making processes and negatively impact patient care. Challenges in Care Coordination:* Although vertical integration is designed to improve coordination, it can sometimes lead to confusion regarding patient care protocols, particularly when transitioning between levels of care (e.g., primary to specialty). A study published in *BMC Health Services Research* found that despite efforts, transitions often result in poor communication and misunderstanding, affecting continuity of care (Greenwood-Lee, 2018). *Focus on Profitability:* Integrated systems may prioritize financial performance over patient care. Research has shown that organizations can sometimes shift focus towards maximizing revenue from high-margin services, potentially compromising the quality of care in less profitable areas.

In conclusion, while vertically integrated healthcare models aim to provide seamless patient care, they carry notable disadvantages that can impact patient experience, service quality, and overall healthcare costs. Addressing these disadvantages requires continued evaluation and adjustments in policy and management strategies.

Evidence for challenges: Integration and Coordination Issues Despite the aim of providing coordinated care, achieving true integration within various levels of care can be difficult. Fragmented communication can exist even within a single organization. Cultural Differences Among Providers, Different specialties and operational units may have varying cultures, leading to conflicts and misunderstandings in care delivery. High Fixed Costs Vertically integrated organizations

require significant investments in infrastructure and technology, which can lead to high fixed costs. Resistance to Change, Healthcare professionals may resist new workflows and collaborative practices required by integration (Mareš, J et al., 2018).

VERTICALLY INTEGRATED HEALTHCARE SERVICE MODEL AROUND THE WORLD, ESPECIALLY IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

In this overview of Integrated care delivery model, Mounier et al., 2017 highlighted following:

Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs): Integrated Care Definition: Often viewed through the lens of continuity of care across levels of the health system. A common approach involves integrating services for specific populations or conditions. Target Populations: Pregnant women, children, individuals with infectious diseases (e.g., HIV, TB), and vulnerable populations. Integration Approaches: Focuses on improving access, convenience, and efficiency, often leveraging existing services to enhance uptake of other essential services. Common models include integrating HIV and reproductive health services, outreach services, and Integrated Management of Childhood Illnesses (IMCI). Challenges: Siloed funding, limited resources, lack of incentives for program integration, inadequate workforce training, poor Health Management Information Systems (HMIS), and fragmented services across agencies. Impact: Evidence on the impact of integrated care in LMICs is limited, with a few studies suggesting increased service utilization and improved health outcomes. However, cost-effectiveness data are scarce. Cross-Cutting Themes and Lessons Learned: Common Challenges: Both HICs and LMICs face challenges related to fragmented services, resource limitations, and workforce issues. However, the specific challenges and their severity differ significantly. Differing Priorities: HICs prioritize improving quality of care and patient experience, while LMICs focus on increasing access to services and improving efficiency. Potential for Mutual Learning: The article argues that both HICs and LMICs can learn from each other's experiences. LMICs can benefit from HICs' patient-centric approaches, while HICs can draw lessons from LMICs' successful strategies for task-shifting and expanding access to essential services. Better integration of prevention and treatment services across all settings is also highlighted as a key area for improvement.

VERTICALLY INTEGRATED HEALTHCARE IN VIETNAM

Vietnam's Vertically Integrated Healthcare: A Challenging Path to Transformation. While the global healthcare landscape has seen a push towards vertical integration, Vietnam's journey towards a fully integrated system remains fraught with challenges. While acknowledging the benefits of integrated care, the reality on the ground reveals a system grappling with several obstacles. In the World

Bank report by Teo, Hui Sin et al (2020). Some key challenges still existed to resolve before implementing integrated care model in Vietnam:

Challenges in Vietnam's Healthcare System: Hospital-Centric Model: The current system prioritizes hospitals, leading to overcrowding, inefficiency, and a lack of emphasis on primary care. Almost half of all outpatient visits occur in hospitals, highlighting the imbalance in the system. **Fragmented Care:** A lack of cohesive coordination between different care providers and settings creates gaps in patient care, contributing to inefficiencies and potentially adverse events.

GAP NEED TO BE RESEARCH FURTHER IN INTEGRATED CARE MODEL

Mixed Evidence on Patient Outcomes: While some studies show improvements in patient-centered outcomes, the evidence base remains weak and inconsistent, particularly concerning patient experience and long-term clinical outcomes.

Limited Impact on Costs: While proponents argue for cost savings associated with vertical integration, the evidence is not conclusive. Some studies suggest benefits, but others highlight potential cost increases or no significant impact.

Difficulties in Measuring Impact: Identifying and measuring changes in performance over time due to vertical integration presents a significant challenge, leading to gaps in the evidence base.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

RQ1: How to design and implement model of vertically integrated care (possibly micro-horizontal combined) for breast cancer and coronary disease services.

RQ2: What impact is vertically integrated care model having the use in specialised care hospital?

RQ3: What impact is vertical integration having on the patient journey with regard to overall experience of care? How differ the experience of multi co-existing morbidities patients versus one/without co-morbidity patients?

RQ4: What impact is vertical integration having on the medical and hospital administrative staffs focusing on the effectiveness of physician-hospital integration, intero-professional integration and medico-administrative integration scale?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Identify key challenges and opportunities of the precondition: Explore the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing vertical integration within the chosen private hospital system.

Develop a participatory action plan for implementing vertically integrated care for breast cancer and prostate cancer service lines.

Evaluate the impact of the integrated system: Assess the impact of the implemented changes on patient's overall experience, quality of care, staff engagement/empowerment.

Assess the impact of vertically integrated care implemented in two service lines on the effectiveness and scale of integration between key stakeholders: physician-hospital, intero-professionals and medico-administration.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Participatory Action Research (PAR) was chosen for this study, as following diagram.

Research model suggested:

Participants' recruitment:

Key managers: one of hospital BoD as senior consultant of each service unit, director of unit must be a key physician, other physicians (4 physicians for each disease unit), RNs in charge at relevant departments, related departments' administrators, one coordinator for each disease services line.

Figure 2: Research Model

Publishing an executive order of BoD for establishing Vertically-Integrated Healthcare Service (Breast cancer and coronary diseases- focusing on acute coronary syndrome) models and how it works, co-operate with others within hospital and with intero-organizational hospitals and outsiders, mechanism of reporting, auditing and expanding, transforming.

Phase 1: Initiative and design Phase (2 months): Stakeholder Identification and Engagement: Identify and engage key stakeholders (patients, physicians, nurses, administrators, government officials, payers, etc.) from the chosen private healthcare system.

Needs Assessment: Conduct a thorough needs assessment to identify existing challenges in the healthcare system, focusing on fragmentation, inefficiencies, and unmet needs. Utilize surveys, interviews, focus groups, and document reviews.

Vertical Integration Model Design: Based on the needs assessment, collaboratively design a tailored vertical integration model with stakeholders. This involves defining which services to integrate, how information will be shared, and what new systems/processes are needed.

Ethical Review and Permissions: Secure necessary ethical approvals from relevant institutional review boards and obtain informed consent from all participants.

Phase 2: Experiment and Execution Phase (10 months): Pilot Implementation (experiment): Implement the designed vertical integration model on a pilot scale within a specific part of the chosen healthcare system. This allows for iterative improvements based on ongoing feedback. Data Collection: Continuously collect data throughout the implementation phase using multiple methods: Quantitative Data: Track KPIs (patient wait times, readmission rates, patient satisfaction scores, cost per patient, staff productivity, etc.). Qualitative Data: Conduct regular interviews, focus groups, and observations to document experiences and challenges. Document reviews can also be valuable. Iterative Adjustments: Based on data collected, regularly review and adjust the vertical integration model. This is a key element of PAR.

Phase 3: Monitoring and expansion Phase (2 months): Evaluation: Conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the implemented vertical integration model. This involves analyzing quantitative and qualitative data to assess its impact on the identified KPIs. Dissemination: Disseminate findings through publications, presentations, and reports to relevant stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the community. Recommendations: Develop evidence-based recommendations for replicating and scaling up successful aspects of the model in other Vietnamese private healthcare systems.

Phase 4: Consolidation and transformation: Transforming from clinical and administrative integration into financial integration with a bundle payment package. Set new possible services that can be transformed from conventional delivery into integrated delivery.

Expected findings: Scale of Integration, Patient's outcomes (clinical outcomes and patient's overall experience) and business outcomes (turnover, profitability, service reputation?). Scale of integration; Scale of coordination and Medical professionals engagement; Physician satisfaction; Patient's outcomes: clinical and overall experience; Business outcomes: revenue growth rates, cost of services in entire care, volume of patient growth, community and patient's recognition

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

Theoretical contributions: Improved Care Coordination. Increased Efficiency and Cost Savings (Potentially).

Key Considerations for Adaptation: Start Small and Focus, Prioritize Primary Care, t. Leverage Existing Resources, Community Engagement, Sustainable Financing.

Practical execution contribution: exploring the value-based and team-based care and value-based payment in modern healthcare service business.

Social implication: How vertical integration alone or combining with horizontal integration can resolve the fragmentation existing in public healthcare institution? How integrated care services can expand to broader scope of healthcare service management in mass population health care policy?

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